

Corrigendum to “Multiple Steady States for Chemical Reaction Networks of Deficiency One,”
Archive for Rational Mechanics and Analysis, **132** (1995), 371-406.

Equation (4.7) on page 388 should read as follows:

$$\sigma_s = p_s(\exp(\mu_s) - 1), \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$$